

EFFECTS OF GREEN SYNTHESIZED SILVER NITRATE NANOPARTICLES AND BONE MEAL ON THE PRODUCTIVITY OF SESAME (*Sesamum indicum* L.)

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effects of silver nitrate nanoparticles and bone meal on the growth and yield of sesame (*Sesamum indicum*) in Makurdi, Nigeria. A factorial experimental design was adopted, with treatments consisting of varying concentrations of silver nitrate (200ppm, 400ppm, 600ppm, 800ppm) and bone meal (5g, 10g, 15g, 20g). Growth parameters, including plant height, leaf length, stem diameter, and yield parameters such as the number of seeds per plant and seed weight, were measured. Data were collected biweekly over 12 weeks and analysed using ANOVA with significance set at $p < 0.05$. There were no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in plant growth parameters except leaf width of 2.22cm to 4.96cm in the pre-treatment investigation. Application of $AgNO_3$ nanoparticles (400-800ppm) caused significant increases in plant height and leaf length ($p < 0.05$) from 40-60DAP. Bone meal at 10g influenced the growth of stem diameter at 60 DAP. Silver nitrate nanoparticles at 600-800 ppm significantly increased the number of seeds (82-85 seeds) while bone meal at 5g yielded the highest wet biomass (>60g) and dry biomass (<25g). Silver nitrate nanoparticles increased growth performances and biological yield while bone meal increased growth and physiological yield. Hence, both silver nitrate nanoparticles and bone meal are recommended as alternative fertilizers in boosting the productivity of sesame in Nigeria.

Key words: silver nitrate nanoparticle, bone meal, *Sesamum indicum*, performance

INTRODUCTION

Sesame, also known as benniseed (*Sesamum indicum* L), is an important oilseed crop grown in many parts of the world. Known for its high oil content and rich nutritional profile, sesame seeds are widely used in cooking, confectionery, and pharmaceutical industries. The seeds are a source of essential fatty acids, proteins, vitamins, and minerals, making them a significant component of human nutrition and a valuable crop for farmers (Nzikou *et al.*, 2009; Pathak *et al.*, 2014). Despite its economic and nutritional importance, sesame cultivation often faces several

Challenges

Poor soil infestations, and suboptimal agricultural practices can lead to reduced yields and lower-quality seeds (Olowe and Busari, 2000). Enhancing soil fertility and improving crop management practices are critical for increasing productivity and ensuring sustainable agricultural practices (Ali *et al.*, 2019; Adekola *et al.*, 2020).

Traditional soil amendments, such as bone meal, have been used to improve soil fertility and promote plant growth (Olasan *et al.*, 2021). Bone meal is an organic fertilizer derived from animal bones and is rich in phosphorus and calcium. These

nutrients are essential for plant development, particularly for root growth and seed production (Havlin *et al.*, 2014). However, the use of bone meal alone may not be sufficient to address all the challenges of low productivity in sesame cultivation. In recent years, advancements in nanotechnology have introduced novel approaches to enhancing crop growth and productivity. Silver nitrate nanoparticles, in the form of bone meal, were thoroughly washed with distilled water, soaked for 8 hours (80°C to 90°C), and dried for 72 hours and grinded into a fine powder using mortar and pestle. The powder and bone meal were then sieved (through a 75 µm sieve) to ensure uniform particle size for efficient silver application on the crop (Olesina *et al.*, 2021). Silver nitrate addressing the challenges from Fumeco Chemical Company, there is limited research on the combined effects of these treatments on the crop. This study sought to fill this knowledge gap by investigating how bone meal and silver nitrate nanoparticles could influence sesame growth, development, and yield. The aim of the study was to determine the effect of green synthesized silver nitrate nanoparticles and bone meal on the productivity of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L) in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This research work was carried out in Makurdi, the Capital of Benue State in Nigeria. The city is located in the middle belt, along the Benue River. Makurdi town lies between Latitude 7° 44'N and Longitude 8° 32'E covering an area of 820km² with its last estimated population known to be 342,500 people (NPC, 2006). Farming is the mainstay of livelihood among the people. Intercropping of sesame farming with other legumes such as cowpea and groundnut is common. The study was

conducted in the Botanical Garden of the Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria

Sample Collection and Preparation

Viable sesame seeds (white variety) were purchased from Wurukum market while pieces of bones harvested from cow butchering were collected as wastes from Wurukum abattoir in the study area. The soil, with pre-existing physicochemical properties, was collected from the Botanical Garden of the Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University. Soil was collected, sieved and filled into Forty- Five pots (45), each with 25kg of the sieved soil, based on the experimental design, in preparation for seed sowing.

Green Synthesis of Silver Nitrate Nanoparticle

The procedures outlined in Sathishkumar *et al.* (2010) and Fayomi *et al.* (2024) were followed. Fresh leaves of *Jatropha tanjorensis* were harvested, prepared, air dried and grinded using electric blender. Exactly 6g of the product was mixed with 100mL of double distilled water in a beaker, and heated at 80°C for 1 hour. Exactly 1 mM of Silver nitrate was added to the extract and allowed to stand for 1hr. The resulting paste was calcined in a furnace at 400 °C for about 2hr then the residual was washed by ethanol and distilled water several times. The powder was then heated at 100 °C to dry.

Experimental Design

The experiment was designed using a

complete randomised method with powdered bone meal and silver nitrate nanoparticles as treatments, each with five levels replicated five times. The silver nitrate nanoparticle treatment was applied at 200,400,600 and 800ppm while bone meal had the following levels: 2.5, 10, 15 and 20g. There were 45 experimental units in total (40 treated pots and 5 control pots) (Olasan et al., 2021).

Seed Sowing

Three seeds were sown in each pot at 3cm depth and watered twice daily. Pots were protected from external influences using locally constructed nets.

Pre-treatment characterization of seedlings at 20 Day After Planting (DAP)

The adopted experimental design is stated above. Seedlings were characterized at 20 DAP before treatment application. Standard description guide was used in determination of plant height, leaf length, leaf width and number of leaves (Aguoru et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2021).

Treatment Applications

Treatments were applied using the foliar application method as described by Ali et al. (2019). Treatment levels specified in the experimental design were followed. Silver nitrate nanoparticle was dispensed using the micro pipette while powdered bone meal of known quantity was applied using the spatula (Olasan et al., 2021). . **Assessment of Growth Parameters at 40, 60 and 80 DAP** Standard procedures were adopted (Aguoru et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2021). Plant height was determined using the meter rule in centimetres (cm). All the leaves and branches in the plant stand present in the pot were counted. Leaf were measured in centimetres (cm). Stem diameter was determined by measuring the distance between the widest parts of the

stem with a meter rule in centimeter (cm).

Flowering and Biological Yield

The procedures outlined in Hossain et al. (2021) were used. The day to flowering was determined by recording the day the plant first produced flower after seed sowing. The number of pods produced by the plant was counted. The pod length was determined using a meter rule the stalk or peduncle in centimetres (cm). After maturity and harvesting, number of seeds present in each pod was counted per pot. Pod weight and seed weight were determined using the digital weighing balance and recorded in gram (g).

Determination of Physiological Yield Wet and dry plant biomass

One fresh mature plant collected from each pot was weighed using the weighing balance after soil had been removed from the root. This was taken as the wet plant biomass (g). The plant was oven dried in oven at 200°C for 12 hours to remove the moisture content. This was recorded as the dry plant biomass (g) (AOAC, 2000).

Determination of fibre

The fibre content was determined using the neutral detergent fibre (NDF) method (AOAC, 2000). Approximately 1 gram of dried and ground plant sample was weighed and placed in a filter bag, which was then submerged in a neutral detergent solution. The sample was heated for one hour at 100°C to dissolve soluble components, leaving the fibrous material. After cooling, the filter bag was rinsed with hot water and dried in an oven at 105°C for 24 hours. The dried sample was then weighed, and the fibre content was calculated as the percentage of the initial sample weight that remained after the treatment. The fibre content was determined using the formula: $\text{Fibre Content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of dried residue (g)}}{\text{Initial sample weight (g)}} \times 100$

Determination of chlorophyll This was determined using the standard method of AOAC (2000). A quantity of 0.1 g of fresh leaves of Cowpea seed was collected and placed into a test tube filled

with 10 ml of acetone. The test tube was then incubated in a dark environment at 4°C for 24 hours to generate a green extract.

Subsequently, the green extract was transferred to a cuvette for spectrophotometric measurement, where the absorbance was recorded at 663 nm for chlorophyll a and at 645 nm for chlorophyll b. The Chlorophyll content was determined using the formula:

$$\text{Total Chlorophyll Content: Total Chl (mg/g)} = (8.2 \times A_{663}) + (20.2 \times A_{645})$$

Statistical Analysis

Minitab 17 software was used for data analysis. One-way ANOVA was recorded in plants treated with bone meal at 10g. Thus, performance among the treatments. Mean separation was done using the Fisher LSD method while bone meal at 10g increased stem diameter of sesame at 60 DAP

ranged between 6.80cm (bone meal at 20g) to 13.30cm in silver nitrate nanoparticle at 400ppm. Stem diameter ranged from 1.80cm in bone meal at 10g to 3.06 cm in silver nitrate nanoparticle at 400ppm. Thus,

AgNO₃ nanoparticle significantly influenced plant height, leaf sizes and stem diameter at concentrations of 400-800ppm. Table 3 gives the effect of silver nitrate nanoparticles and powdered bone meals as organic manure (OG) at different concentrations on the growth parameters of sesame at 60 DAP. Significant differences in

treatment means were recorded in plant heights, leaf length and leaf stem diameter (p<0.05). Plant height ranged from 120.00cm in control pot to 153.00cm silver nitrate nanoparticles at 800ppm. The longest leaf measured was 13.3cm in silver nanoparticles at 400ppm while the

longest leaf measured was 13.3cm in silver nanoparticles at 400ppm while the

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary Characterisation and effects of treatments on the growth parameters of sesame plant 40 -60 DAP

Table 1 gives the preliminary characterisation of growth parameters of sesame before treatment at 20 DAP (day after planting). There were no significant differences (P>0.05) in all growth parameters of plants in the pots except leaf width, which ranged from 2.22cm to 4.96cm. Table 2 gives the effect of AgNO₃ (200 ppm-800 ppm) and bone meal at (5g-20g) on the growth parameters of sesame at 40DAP. Significant differences were recorded in treatment means of plant height, leaf length, stem diameter (p<0.05). The result showed that the silver nitrate nanoparticle-treated plant had the tallest height (142.20cm) at 800ppm. Leaf Length

Application of AgNO₃ nanoparticles (400-800ppm) caused significant increases in plant height and leaf sizes from 40-60DAP. Silver nitrate nanoparticles (AgNO₃ NPs) are known for their ability to stimulate plant growth by enhancing nutrient uptake. Bone meal could be applied as cheap animal waste and organic fertilizer, being rich in phosphorus and calcium, which are essential nutrients for plant growth. These results align with previous studies that emphasise the importance of bone meal in promoting plant growth, especially in phosphorus-deficient soils (Havlin *et al.*, 2014). In this work, bone meal at 10g influenced only the growth of stem diameter but not height and foliar parameters. This suggests that while bone meal can enhance certain growth metrics, its effects might be limited without additional nutrient sources.

The study demonstrated that plants treated with silver nitrate nanoparticles, especially at higher concentrations showed superior performance in terms of plant height and leaf size. This indicates that silver nitrate nanoparticles may have a more pronounced effect on promoting vertical growth in sesame. Moreover, the nanoparticles positively influenced leaf expansion, which could improve photosynthetic efficiency. These results are consistent with studies that reported the growth-promoting effects of silver nanoparticles on plants due to their

ability to enhance water and nutrient absorption (Rastogi *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, the antimicrobial properties of silver nanoparticles may have contributed to reducing the impact of soil-borne pathogens, allowing for healthier root systems and better overall plant development. Results align with reports on the role of green-synthesised nanoparticles in enhancing the growth and yield of different food crops for sustaining agriculture (Mousavi *et al.*, 2020; Okwu *et al.*, 2021; Fayomi *et al.*, 2024).

Table 1. Preliminary evaluation of Sesame trials at day 20 without treatment application

Treatments	Plant height at day 20(cm)	Number of plant at day 20	Number of leaves at day 20	Leaf Length at day 20 (cm)	Leaf width at day 20 (cm)
Pot1	7.30 ±1.70	3.60 ±0.55	±1.89 6.50	±1.93 4.44	2.22 ±0.62 ^d
Pot2	6.00 ±3.62	4.00 ±0.71	±1.23 8.00	±2.36 4.12	2.720 ±1.21 ^{cd}
Pot3	7.22 ±1.41	4.40 ±0.55	±1.58 7.60	±0.71 5.50	2.30 ±0.47 ^d
Pot4	7.16 ±0.80	4.00 ±1.00	±1.14 7.80	±1.56 5.22	3.64 ±1.28 ^{bc}
Pot5	8.36 ±0.49	3.00 ±0.71	±1.92 8.60	±1.19 4.32	3.90 ±1.01 ^{ab}
Pot6	8.30 ±0.44	3.40 ±0.55	±0.55 8.40	±0.51 5.44	4.02 ±0.92 ^{ab}
Pot7	8.00 ±0.53	4.20 ±0.84	±0.55 7.80	±0.63 4.46	3.66 ±0.52 ^{ab}
Pot8	8.34 ±0.84	3.40 ±0.55	±1.26 8.10	±1.40 4.54	4.08 ±0.51 ^{ab}
Pot9	8.42 ±0.61	3.60 ±0.55	±0.74 0.379	±2.49 0.827	4.96 ±0.40 ^a
P-VALUE	0.199 (P>0.05)	0.057 (P>0.05)	(P>0.05) NS	(P>0.05) NS	0.000 (P<0.05)
LSD	NS	NS			1.066

Table 2: Effects of nano and organic manure on growth parameters at 40 DAP

Treatments	Plant height at day 40 (cm)	Number of plants at day 40	Number of leaves at day 40	Leaf Length at day 40 (cm)	Number of branches at day 40	Leaf width at day 40 (cm)	Stem diameter at day 40 (cm)
C	101.60 ±13.52 ^b	3.40 ±0.55	50.20 ±7.26	11.42 ±1.19 ^b	±1.30 1.60	7.06 ±2.36	2.90 ±0.58 ^{ab}
NA200ppm	106.00 ±19.17 ^b	2.60 ±0.55	37.60 ±12.70	11.84 ±1.58 ^{ab}	±1.34 2.00	7.50 ±0.71	2.67 ±0.43 ^{ab}
NA400ppm	109.40 ±12.50 ^b	3.20 ±0.84	46.40 ±1.14	13.30 ±1.57 ^a	±1.23 1.20	6.50 ±1.41	3.06 ±0.62 ^d
NA600ppm	111.20 ±25.70 ^b	3.20 ±1.10	41.20 ±12.54	11.40 ±2.61 ^b	±1.30 1.20	7.28 ±1.64	2.40 ±0.31 ^{bcd}
NA800ppm	142.20 ±5.36 ^a	3.40 ±0.55	40.00 ±15.25	11.60 ±0.42 ^{ab}	±1.01 1.60	7.10 ±0.74	2.60 ±0.52 ^{abc}
OG5g	137.00 ±16.51 ^a	3.40 ±0.55	47.60 ±14.08	12.38 ±0.86 ^{ab}	±1.14 1.40	6.20 ±2.51	2.46 ±0.46 ^{abc}
OG10g	135.80 ±9.09 ^a	3.60 ±0.55	39.60 ±9.02	12.66 ±0.88 ^{ab}	±1.52 1.20	7.30 ±2.54	4.80 ±0.27 ^a
OG15g	135.80 ±16.57 ^a	3.20 ±0.45	35.00 ±1.00	7.10 ±1.08 ^c	±2.17 1.20	6.90 ±1.14	2.70 ±0.45 ^{ab}
OG20g	139.00 ±10.93 ^a	3.60 ±0.55	39.20 ±11.48	6.80 ±0.57 ^c	±0.00 0.410	5.50 ±1.97	2.00 ±0.50 ^{cd}
P-VALUE	0.000	0.418	0.367	0.000		0.748	0.003
LSD	19.731	NS	NS	1.723	NS	NS	0.603

LSD indicates Least Significant Difference (p=0.05); OG: Organic Manure treatment, NA: Nano treatment; NS = Not significant

Table 3: Effects of nano and organic manure on growth parameters at 60 DAP

Treatments	Plant height at day 60 (cm)	Number of plants at day 60	Number of leaves at day 60	Leaf Length at day 60 (cm)	Number of branches at day 60	Leaf width at day 60 (cm)	Stem diameter at day 60 (cm)
C	120.00 ±15.8 ^d	3.40 ±0.55	±4.83 48.80	11.42 ±1.19 ^b	2.20 ±1.30	7.06 ±2.36	2.90 ±0.58 ^{ab}
NA200ppm	120.00 ±18.03 ^d	2.60 ±0.55	±12.32 61.00	11.84 ±1.58 ^{ab}	1.60 ±1.34	7.50 ±0.71	2.67 ±0.43 ^{ab}
NA400ppm	125.00 ±14.21 ^{cd}	3.20 ±0.84	±6.04 56.40	13.30 ±1.57 ^a	2.00 ±1.23	6.50 ±1.41	3.06 ±0.62 ^a
NA600ppm	126.80 ±27.70 ^{bcd}	3.20 ±1.10	±16.04 65.80	11.40 ±2.61 ^b	1.20 ±1.30	7.28 ±1.64	2.40 ±0.31 ^{bcd}
NA800ppm	153.20 ±9.12 ^a	3.40 ±0.55	±18.75 53.20	11.60 ±0.42 ^{ab}	1.20 ±1.30	7.10 ±0.74	2.60 ±0.52 ^{abc}
OG5g	147.80 ±19.04 ^{ab}	3.60 ±0.55	±14.82 51.40	12.38 ±0.86 ^{ab}	1.60 ±1.14	6.20 ±2.51	2.46 ±0.46 ^{abc}
OG10g	147.80 ±10.76 ^{ab}	±0.45 3.60	±9.81 45.00	12.66 ±0.88 ^{ab}	1.40 ±1.52	7.30 ±2.54	1.80 ±0.27 ^d
OG15g	147.00 ±20.49 ^{abc}	0.418 (P>0.05)	±1.00) 47.80	7.10 ±1.08 ^c	1.20 ±2.17	6.90 ±1.14	2.70 ±0.45 ^{ab}
OG20g	152.20 ±13.37 ^a	NS	±8.58 0.074	6.80 ±0.57 ^c	0.00 ±0.00	5.50 ±1.97	2.00 ±0.50 ^{cd}
P-VALUE	0.005 (P<0.05)		(P>0.05	(P<0.05	(P>0.05	(P>0.05)	(P<0.05)
LSD	22.168	NS	NS	1.723	NS	NS	0.603

LSD indicates Least Significant Difference (p=0.05); OG: Organic Manure treatment, NA: Nano treatment; NS = Not significant

Effects of silver nitrate and bone meal manure on biological yield parameters of cowpea

Table 4 gives the effects of silver nitrate nanoparticles and powdered bone meals on flowering, pod and seed yield of sesame.

Treatments did not affect all parameters of biological yield except seed quantity which varied significantly from 55 seeds in bone meal at 20g to 85 seeds when silver nitrate nanoparticles were applied to sesame at 600 ppm while 800 ppm of the treatment yielded 82 seeds. Thus, silver nitrate nanoparticles at 600-800 ppm influenced only the number of seeds in sesame plants. Treatments did not affect biological yield such as number height and yield. Results align with other studies on the effects of fertilizers application on sesame growth and yield (Hossain et al., 2021). Significantly increased the number of seeds (82-85 seeds), indicating that this treatment

may be more effective in maximizing yield compared to bone meal. However, bone meal still played a crucial role in improving the physiological yield through biomass production. Bone meal applied at 5g significantly yielded the highest wet biomass (>60g) and dry biomass (<25g). This result is in tandem with Mofeed et al.

Table 4: Effects of nano and organic manure on flowering and yield parameters

Treatments	Day to flowering of pods	Number of pods	Pod length (cm)	Number of seeds per pod	Total Pod weight (g)	Total seed weight
C	47.20	40.00	3.20	78.80	0.20	0.19
	±4.32	±7.31	±0.27	3.40	±0.21	±0.01
NA200ppm	52.60	39.80	3.30	81.20	0.33	0.19
	±3.36	±12.70	±0.27	±14.67 ^{ab}	±0.02	±0.02
NA400ppm	52.40	40.20	3.30	66.40	0.29	0.21
	±10.16	±12.46	±0.27	±17.26 ^{bc}	±0.11	±0.03
NA600ppm	51.60	40.40	3.30	85.80	0.26	0.18
	±8.91	±10.21	±0.27	3.40	±0.21	±0.02
NA800ppm	49.40	41.60	3.60	82.00	0.22	0.23
	±4.16	±8.62	±0.42	±11.47 ^{ab}	±0.01	±0.00
OG5g	55.20	49.00	0.466	66.80	0.31	0.25
	±9.55	±5.61	(P>0.05)	(P=0.09) ^{bc}	(P>0.05)	±0.03
OG10g	50.20	40.00		66.20	0.35	0.20
	±8.07	±5.10		±19.79 ^{bc}	±0.01	±0.02
OG15g	45.80	41.20		70.00	0.26	0.20
	±2.39	±4.27		±12.08 ^{abc}	±0.02	±0.01
OG20g	56.20	32.80		53.20	0.21	0.24
	±6.53	±12.87		±13.48 ^c	±0.01	±0.01
P-VALUE	0.318 (P>0.05)	0.484 (P>0.05)		0.011	0.486	0.310 (P>0.05)
	NS	NS				NS
LSD			NS	17.182	NS	

LSD indicates Least Significant Difference (p=0.05); OG: Organic Manure treatment, NA: Nano treatment; NS =Notsignificant

Effects of silver nitrate nanoparticle and bone meal on the physiological yield of cowpea Treatments produced significant effects on only plant biomass among the physiological yield parameters investigated. Bone meal applied at 5g significantly yielded the highest wet biomass (>60g) and dry biomass (<25g) as shown in Figures 1 and 2. The outcome is in tandem with the work of Olasan *et al.* (2021), who found that animal- based manures (bone meal, earthworm cast and crab shell) improved biomass. Treatments did not impact positively on the

seed fibre content and leaf chlorophyll as the control group had the highest values for these biochemical properties as shown in Figures 3 and 4. From the study, it appears that one particular treatment is insufficient to completely influence sesame productivity. Due to the preference of sesame for nutrient enriched soil (Moges *et al.*, 2018), a combined treatment approach is recommended while other cheap treatment sources that may enhance pod yield may be incorporated as soil fertilizers.

The pooled standard deviation was used to calculate the intervals.

Figure 1: Interval Plot of Wet Plant Biomass vs Treatments (95% CI for the mean)
 Keys: NA20 = 200ppmnanoparticle; NA40 =400ppm nanoparticle, NA60 = 600ppm nanoparticle, NA80 = 800ppm nanoparticle; OG20 = 5g organic bone meal; OG40 = 10.0g organic bone meal; OG60 = 15g organic bone meal, OG80 = 20g organic bone meal

The pooled standard deviation was used to calculate the intervals.

Figure 2: Interval Plot of Dry Plant Biomass vs Treatments (95% CI for the mean)
 Keys: NA20 = 200ppm nanoparticle; NA40 = 400ppm nanoparticle, NA60 = 600ppm nanoparticle, NA80 = 800ppm nanoparticle; OG20 = 5g organic bone meal; OG40 = 10.0g organic bone meal; OG60 = 15g organic bone meal, OG80 = 20g organic bone meal

The pooled standard deviation was used to calculate the intervals.

Figure 3: Interval Plot of Fibre vs Treatments (95% CI for the mean)
 Keys: NA20 = 200ppm nanoparticle; NA40 = 400ppm nanoparticle, NA60 = 600ppm nanoparticle, NA80 = 800ppm nanoparticle; OG20 = 5g organic bone meal; OG40 = 10.0g organic bone meal; OG60 = 15g organic bone meal, OG80 = 20g organic bone meal

The pooled standard deviation was used to calculate the intervals.

Figure 4: Interval Plot of Chlorophyll content vs Treatments (95% CI for the mean)

Keys: NA20 = 200ppmnanoparticle; NA40 =400ppm nanoparticle, NA60 = 600ppm nanoparticle, NA80 = 800ppm nanoparticle; OG20 = 5g organic bone meal; OG40 = 10.0g organic bone meal; OG60 = 15g organic bone meal, OG80 = 20g organic bone meal

CONCLUSION

Silver nitrate nanoparticles increased growth performances (plant height and number of leaves) and biological yield (number of seeds) while bone meal increased aspects of growth (stem diameter)

and physiological yield (plant biomass). Hence, both silver nitrate nanoparticles at 400-800ppm) and bone meal (5-10g) are recommended as alternative fertilizers in boosting the productivity of sesame in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Adekola, O., Adewumi O. and Faleyimu, O. (2020). Mechanization for improving sesame production in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Mechanization*, 14(3): 65-72.
- Ali, M., Hussain, M., Ahmed, M. and Rizwan, M. (2019). Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) productivity under different soil moisture levels and foliar zinc application. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 21(1): 135-142
- Aguoru, C.U., Okoli, B.E. and Olasan, J.O. (2016). Comparative Gross morphology of some species of *Sesamum* L. *International Journal of Current Research in BioSciences and Plant Biology*, 3(5): 21-32.
- AOAC (2000). Official Method of Analysis. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington, DC, USA. 17th edition.
- Fayomi, O.M., Olasan, J.O., Aguru, C.U., Anjorin, T.S. and Sule, A.M. (2024). Effect of Biosynthesized ZnO Nanoparticles Derived from *Jatropha tajonensis* on the yield of Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranean* L.). *African Journal of Agriculture and Allied Sciences*, 4(1): 192-212
- Havlin, J.L., Beaton, J.D., Tisdale, S.L. and Nelson, W.L. (2014). Soil Fertility and Fertilizers: An Introduction to Nutrient Management (8th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education.
- Hossain, M.A., Islam, M.A., Haque, M.M. and Khatun, M.R. (2021). Effect of fertilizer application on sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) growth, yield, and oil content. *Journal of Agronomy*, 20(1): 20-29.
- Mofeed, J.M., Al-Mutairi, K.A. and Saleh, M.M. (2022). Influence of organic amendments on biomass and chlorophyll content in legumes. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 45(4): 552-564.
- Moges, A., Adugna, A. and Diriba, G. (2018). Soil fertility status of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) growing areas in North Western Ethiopia. *Agriculture and Biology Journal of North America*, 9(2): 35-45.
- Mousavi SM, Lahouti M, Ganjeali A and Entezari MH. (2020). Investigating the effect of titanium dioxide nanoparticles (TiO₂ NPs) on growth and biochemical characteristics of barley under salinity stress. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 43(11): 1643-1655.
- Nzikou, J.M., Mvoula-Tsieri, M., Matos, L., Ndangui, C.B., Pambou-Tobi, N.P.G., Kimbonguila, A., S. T., Linder, M. and Desobry, S. (2009). Chemical composition on the seeds and oil of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) grown in Congo-Brazzaville. *Advance Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 1(1): 6-11.
- Okwu, D.E., Ogbonna, J.C. and Ndukwu, B.I. (2021). The role of titanium dioxide nanoparticles in enhancing growth parameters of legumes. *International Journal of Agronomy and Agricultural Research*, 16(1): 25-34.
- Olasan, J.O., Aguru, C.U., Omoigui, L.O. and Awoji, P. (2021). Effects of Animal Based Manures (Bone

- Meal, Earthworm Cast and Crab Shell) on the Growth of Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.). *Journal of Agricultural Science and Engineering*, 7(3): 43-49.
- Olowe, V.I.O. and Busari, L.D. (2000). Response of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) to nitrogen and phosphorus application in southern Guinea Savanna of Nigeria. *Tropical Oilseeds Journal*, 5(1): 24-30.
- Pathak, N., Rai, A.K., Kumari, R., Thapa, A. and Bhat, K.V. (2014). Sesame crop: An underexploited oilseed holds potential for enhanced food value. *Agricultural Research*, 3(2): 135-145.
- Rastogi, A., Zivcak, M., Sytar, O., Kalaji, H.M., He, X., Mbarki, S. and Brestic, M. (2019). Impact of Metal and Metal Oxide Nanoparticles on Plant: A Critical Review. *Frontiers in Chemistry*, 7: 392.
- Sathishkumar, T., Karthikeyan, S. and Ramesh, S. (2010). Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles from Plant Extracts: An Eco-Friendly Approach. *Journal of Nanotechnology*, Article ID 762473.
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